
The role and involvement of NGOs in activities related to humanitarian issues in Palestine

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Abstract

The colonialism and tyranny of the Palestinian people after the silence of the large-scale countries and the limited support of the *Palestinian National Authority* or the rather westernized capacity of the people, the presence of various types of non-governmental organizations or *non-governmental organizations* (NGOs) carries out humanitarian assistance activities for vulnerable groups. This. The main objective of this research is to recognize the nature of humanity and the contribution of Malaysian Humanitarian NGOs to the Palestinian Humanitarian issue. Based on a qualitative approach, a virtual meeting was held with three members of the Safe Palestine NGO. The selection of this NGO was based on special assistance to the Palestinians and active involvement since the establishment of the organization. The study shows that there are various forms of assistance for humanity, Safe Palestine, through projects involving the economic, educational, social, health, agricultural, and infrastructure sectors that have successfully contributed to the health of people in the world. Active involvement through activities in Malaysia has made awareness of the Palestinian issue among the Malaysian community. However, Safe Palestine projects and activities are considered to be religious. The essence of the Palestinian issue is equated as humanism and not religion solely so that all ethnic groups, regardless of religious background, can go hand in hand in refuting Israel's misanthropy.

Keywords: Safe Palestine, humanitarian issues, Israel, NGO, Israel's misanthropy, non-governmental organizations

Introductions

In 1948, Israel was recognized as a state by the United States and the Soviet Union, which had a direct impact on the Palestinian population regardless of religious status. From that period, approximately 2 million Palestinians were driven out of their settlements because the Jews wanted to be part of the Palestinian land. This incident caused a large number of the worst

Palestinian people to become refugees in other Arab countries such as Syria, Jordan, and Lebanon (Morrar & Baba, 2022). On the other hand, some Palestinian people who are still living in the air face various threats to their safety, such as harassment, harassment, shootings, and shootings in other areas. The Zionists have also lived the Palestinian people under one view of life if there is a barrier to basic utility resources such as water, food, medicine, telecommunications guard, and liberation of begun. For example, Palestinians who work as fishermen can only look for marine products in limited waters close to the coast and may not exceed what is outlined by Israel. This action is because Israel does not want the Palestinian people to be equal and it is certain that it can give the Israelis a lot of profit. The colonialism and tyranny of the Palestinian people. After the silence of the big countries and the limited response of the Palestinian National Authority (PNA) or the silence of the rather western capacity, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) emerged. NGOs play an important role in building democratic structures in Palestinian society and aim to promote the principles of human rights and democracy in the world so that Palestine gets support from other countries. The number of Palestinian NGOs has become increasingly trustworthy, from 1,230 in 2004 to approximately 2,130 in 2009. In 2010, it was estimated that there would be around 2,400 NGOs (Barghouti, 2022).

The Palestine Liberation Organization or more in tone as the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) is the main priority for the Palestinian people Recognizing that NGOs are more active in the field of providing services for the development of Palestine and meeting the demands of their life needs in various aspects. The economy, culture, and politics in the management of NGOs contribute to the development of Palestine. If the decline in the work of the NGOs, then the development of Palestine will be hampered (Woroniciecka-Krzyzanowska, 2022). This is because Palestine has the support of non-governmental organizations. The Palestinian people also see more humanitarian aid efforts that are not going to NGOs. Therefore, based on the difficulties of life and the active involvement of NGOs in calming the lives of the Palestinian people, this review wants to examine for sure what forms of involvement and assistance of Malaysian humanist NGOs in the issue of Palestinian humanization. Indirectly, this wealth can encourage NGOs to raise tangible forms of humanitarian aid concerning Palestine (Sultan et al., 2022).

Literature Review

Human Rights NGO

The principle of NGO kekususu is to improve the quality of life of universal human beings at the level of the vision, mission, and objectives of its establishment. When it comes to social development, the practice is that an NGO offers a variety of services to people, groups, and groups represented by women, youth, workers, students, people with disabilities, and others. The services have the title of human rights, kesishah, social protection, education, culture, and magic on a lay basis. But some NGOs only use the example of MERCY Malaysia (Matshaka & Wielenga, 2022).

In the beginning, the topic of human rights was seen as the internal authority of the nation-state. It would still be true after 1989 if there was a political alliance with human rights that made it equal for NGOs to accept issues that violated humanism. A markedly positive

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increase in human rights promotion activities continued in the twentieth century in the early stream of UN funds with protracted views from representatives of NGOs. Concern for human rights is a part of the internal equating of public equality which gives the adequacy of libertarian attitudes, wealth, and individual welfare. Tangible rights for all human beings can be considered human rights regardless of individual status whether in terms of nation, gender, place of residence, country of origin, ethnicity, religion, skin color, or language. Meanwhile, violations of human rights by individuals, groups, and all human rights have existed for a long time and are still being used today. However, like Brown and the masses, there is increasing awareness in global rankings about stopping assertiveness, providing care, and helping concerned groups (Srivastava, 2022).

The agility of NGOs in obtaining information from sources such as prey, witnesses, injuries, physical evidence, information sharing by other NGOs, newspaper reports, social media, and demonstrations by NGOs as the first actors to be in a place where human rights are concerned. At the same time, NGOs also ask for peace from the common people, civil society, and other actors on issues related to human rights, raising awareness through conducting investigations, documenting, and then disseminating information (Carolei & Bernaz, 2021).

There are two kinds of human rights NGOs namely advocacy and operation. NGOs advocating donations in the fall of the foundation of celebration to side with the aspirations of the organization. This type of NGO can influence the lives of many people to be in line with the policies that are being developed. The main goal of advocacy NGOs is to emphasize correcting unequal powers. An example of advocacy by NGOs in Malaysia is, for example, Tenaganita, which in 1991 was the result of the struggle of female workers in the agricultural and industrial sectors to obtain their rights as workers, proper wages, menstrual rights and to stop gender-based discrimination or violence. The organization has three areas of focus, namely 1) protection of migrants and refugees, 2) anti-trafficking, and 3) accountability and business responsibility. NGO Operations Manakala is a group that operates within the area or group that seeks assistance. This type of NGO is mostly involved in the provision of social services such as air supply, assistance, infrastructure, Pakistan, vocational training, health services, and education programs. An example of an opera-type NGO that has these characteristics is Aman Palestine (Fisher et al., 2022).

That NGOs are professional because of their specially trained accomplices because they are free because they are sponsored by dowry fees and the funds of the common people. NGOs may be named financial *finanhasi* in official institutions but only so far the limited ones are in particular so that they are not under the auspices of religious institutions. However, the interaction between NGOs and the state is in good condition, including partnerships, networks, partnerships, alliances, consortiums, and partnerships that have many economic, social, and cultural sectors. The communication aimed at development with these two actors serves as a motivating force to improve relations between the state and NGOs and foster a more conducive environment (Schweiger, 2022).

Malaysian NGO on Palestine Issues

Since the Israeli partition was launched against the people of Gaza, and Palestine, there have been many international NGOs including Malaysia. For Malaysian NGOs, the fate of the Palestinian people has become one of the main agendas in the mission to raise the issue of human rights internationally (Siang, 2021).

The Prime Global Security Foundation suggested together with other NGOs; Aman Palestine, Aqsa Syarif, Malaysian Institute of Education Free Association (HALUAN), Islamic Relief Malaysia (IRM), Putra Satu Malaysia Club, MERCY Malaysia, Malaysian Relief Agency (MRA) and Viva Palestine Malaysia (VPM) have joined the Association of NGOs Helping Palestine at the Men's World Trade Center (PWTC) on August 15, 2013. The main aim of this forum is to promote and share ideas on how to help Palestine. The former Prime Minister of Malaysia, Tun Mahathir Mohamad who is also the President of the Perdana Global Security Foundation, participated in the number of kuranaan in this force. Tun Mahathir also stated that there was a need for the right strategy and goals to address human rights issues in Palestine and not just the delivery of food and drinks wang ringgit repair more than these things (Mhd Omar et al., 2021).

On October 15, 2014, at Menara TM, Kuala Lumpur, the private agency Telekom Malaysia Berhad (TM) received RM 300,000.00 in cash from three NGOs, namely Aman Palestine, Aqsa Syarif and the Palestine Humane Tube (Media Prima) to equalize humanitarian efforts on Earth. Palestine. In 2013, TM, VADS Berhad (VADS), Malaysia donated RM 20,000.00 to Aman Palestine for going to Gaza ("TM Donates RM300,000", 2014). The Council of Malaysian Islamic Organizations (MAPIM) among non-governmental organizations active in humanitarian issues provided a santama content of RM 65,000.00 for the atrocities of the Palestinian people who are cruel to language and the atrocities of the Zionists on 11 July 2014. According to Mohd. Azmi Abdul Hamid concurrently serves as President of MAPIM in Sinar Harian, MAPIM together with NGOs from Charity Travel Organizations (Peka), Aqsa Syarif, and Inspiration Muhibah India Muslim (IMIM) are actively trying to raise bantanwa funds and criticize Israel's kiyokan. Israel's attack on Gaza in the 50-day war of 2014 has pavememente the spirit of Malaysian NGOs to take to the streets for the most barbaric slashing protests in this century (Kiang & Yunus, 2021).

On August 2, 2014, at Dataran Merdeka, Kuala Lumpur, more than 50,000 Malaysians from a multi-ethnic community, young and old, came to the meeting "Save the Children of Gaza" suggested by VPM and Aqsa Syarif to express mutual solidarity with the people of Gaza and Palestine who have been oppressed since 66 years ago. The skills of Malaysian NGOs in maintaining the space for the Malaysian people to continue to be close to Palestine have more skills to unite Malaysia towards Palestine. Malaysian NGOs are united in the impartiality of all perspectives regardless of the background of any individual to jointly support the Palestinian struggle, especially in raising awareness of the issue of emancipation of the land of Palestine. Besides that, this wealth can indirectly receive donations from Malaysian NGOs to Palestine(Ngo et al., 2021).

Research Method

This study is based on studies of people who investigate the nature and contribution of Aman Palestine as a non-profit organization in Malaysia that is actively engaged in the issue of Palestine. The study was conducted from 2015 to 2017. A qualitative approach was used to combine primary and secondary data to produce topic-based discussions. The primary data was obtained from a chat meeting with three workers who died during the smooth operation of Safe Palestine Langara. The selection of Aman Palestine as an analysis of the NGO study is due to

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its specialization in the Palestinian issue while this organization has been active since its inception. Jadul 1.1 is information about the informants involved in this research:

Table 1.1. List of informants' chatter

<u>Informant</u>	<u>Answer</u>	<u>Date</u>
Mohd Faizal	project manager	May 19, 2015
Safri Awang Sufian	Safe Palestine Chief Director	September 18th
Awang Piut	Safe Executive	2015
Amy Nadya	Management	December 2
Mohd Nor	human resource	2015
	A man	

Metedah, who grew up with Mohd Faizal Safri and Awang Sufian Awang Piut, met in Kajang, Selangor. The chat session with Amy Nadia Mohd Nor was done virtually via email. The reviewer gave me the answers to the questions asked because there is some information that may not have been answered.

Meanwhile, secondary data were obtained from official journals, books, and websites. The results based on primary and secondary data have triangulation techniques that have obtained accuracy and give value to the reliability of the results and discussions. The seventh technique, for example, Mohd Faizal Safri was found boasting on May 19 2015 and if it is plucked in the essence of the verse it is like, clicking on the excerpt at the end of the verse. Aman Palestin started operating at the end of 2004 but at that time it was named "Initiatives". Kemanan Palestine ". The establishment of Aman Palestine is to present and distribute promptly the rights of the Palestinian people in its way. Therefore, Aman Palestine General Question. On January 3, 2006, the registration of Aman Palestine Berhad was approved by Suruhanjaya Syarikat Malaysia (SSM) as a non-profit organization, the establishment of Safe Palestine is to assist in a planned, perpetual and silver manner to the Palestinian people.

As a not-for-profit organization, Aman Palestine has an expert organization of the Steering Committee in which the directors are not directors of aiman perfecta from the organization and do not have a salary. In the opinion of the Steering Committee Experts within the Aman Palestine organization, the aim is to monitor the management of Aman Palestine operations in addition to being a sanctuary for any problems that have an impact. This view can be elicited by writing that equates to "the board of directors is very important for an NGO and is responsible for many specific tasks". These Steering Committee experts do not work properly with Aman Palestine because they have their careers and apart from being a source of reference, the people involved also have the power to make decisions based on the meeting.

Result and Discussion

Palestine Safe Role

The role of Aman Palestine is as a platform for pekkamana kamenanan in Palestine by moving on three foundations, namely humanity, brotherhood, and the sanctity of Baitul Maqdis. In addition, Aman Palestine is a humanitarian NGO that allocates religious, financial, and humane assistance to the Palestinian people in a completely healthy manner. Since its establishment, Aman Palestine has been successful in channeling assistance in the form of various types of projects to the Palestinian people in Palestine (El-Khodary et al., 2021).

In Lebanon and Syria, the proceeds are collected and donated by people. Aman Palestine has the role of being a body that is a source of reference by playing a role in providing assistance and support to the Palestinian people to enjoy a safe and prosperous life by having a measurable professional and quality pilot institution. sincerity, trust, and pride. In addition, this NGO is responsible as an organization to apply awareness and a sense of security in the hearts of the Muslim community in Malaysia to help the Palestinian people as a brotherhood and non-Islamic nations as human beings who have not been affected until now. its activities. Aman Palestine also plays a role in building real projects in various fields in the Palestinian world to help people create a future and continue their lives, as well as accommodate people's urgent needs (Alessandro et al., 2021).

In making the Malaysian people aware of the Palestinian issue, Aman Palestine participates in the function of raising funds and channeling aid through humanization missions to Palestine. Safri (2015) states that Aman Palestine seeks to establish relationships with human rights organizations at home and abroad, as well as collaborate with government agencies and NGOs to ensure that humanitarian assistance can be distributed smoothly. Among other things, the role is to empower activities cooperatively, organize a series of discussion forums, and publish and distribute public distribution materials as an initiative to raise awareness about Palestine. The reviewer also found that Aman Palestine is responsible for making the Malaysian people more aware of the Palestinian issue as a seasonal issue but it is a responsibility that needs to be realized. Apart from that, Aman Palestine wants to convey to the people of Malaysia that the issue of Palestine needs to be known consistently, not only when there are citizens there and this naatadat can also be supported by the Association for the Spread of Islam between Nations, Kamarudin Abdullah. He said the obedience of the Muslim Ummah to the Palestinian people does not change seasonally because the struggle of the Palestinian people to liberate their country from the tyranny of the Zionist regime is a long struggle (Bacchus et al., 2021).

Implementation Project

Since the opening of the Aman Palestine branch office in Gaza in 2009, the project has carried out many projects. The project which is under the auspices of Aman Palestine is for four categories namely Palestinian orphans (180 prequels), poor families (100 prequels), Palestinian martyrs' families (100 per month), and educational assistance (50 per month). Meanwhile, among the projects that have been completed are eight beds at the As-Shifa Hospital Anxiety Department, bus transportation to al-Aqsa, and the development of young Palestine. Apart from that, Aman Palestine is also participating in the kijama project of the deaf conjamsana project of the al-Qassam Mosque in Khan Younis which was destroyed during the war. Palestine has fertile land suitable for agriculture. In connection with that, let Aman Palestine see it as good for running the aribanan project there by the way Aman Palestine has

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prepared funds for aritangan and the Palestinian people themselves will manage the atribanan activities such as the farmland and water pond project in Jabalia. According to him, indirectly this project can help the pagans involve the Palestinian people on agrarian behalf. The roads in the agricultural area have also been affected. As a result of the Israeli partnership, therefore, Safe Palestine has implemented a road system project for the Palestinian people in the Artaniya area. Apart from that, Aman Palestine is also the people of Malaysia to donate to the Al-Quran waqf project because it is a charity program that uses the Al-Quran as material to be gifted. The recipient will receive a certificate from Aman Palestine as a token of gratitude in contact through the waqf concept (Abdul Rashid et al., 2020).

Based on Diagram 1.2, provide more information about the progress of the project in four sectors, Safe Palestine, and a first in the sector. Aman Palestine assisted health care by purchasing two ambulances for medical treatment, providing medical care and medical services to injured people and disadvantaged people. The second sector is air, sanitation, hygiene, and transportation, and this project aims to improve services in certain areas such as Jabalia, Bait Hanoun, Khuzaa, and Bani. Suhaila and Al Shouka . Meanwhile, among the services intended are the type of digger from JCB (4CX), Toyota car service, car oil, water purifier extract, additional waste, and 15 water tanks. Farmers Utilize Vegetable Installation With 10 Km of Mainline Water 4 Inch Diameter. The most important sector is the administrative division that takes care of the vehicle sector at the public and sanctuary offices with various safety sectors such as jackets, lights, oxygen cylinders, hoses, ropes, and generators (Syah, 2019).

Figure 1.2. Early Recovery Plan; Aman Palestine Berhad.

Next was the launch of the Gaza Development and Recovery Tube after the 51-day war in 2014. This project started from 14 September to December 2015 under the 2015 campaign. Other projects carried out by Aman Palestine include the construction of the as-Shafi'i mosque and houses of victims of war and assisting to help those who are underprivileged (Silver, 2021). The impression that the water was almost intoxicated by all the waste and the impression that the highway was in a bad state, Aman Palestine has already hit the jentolak project to destroy the ruins involved. Apart from that, Aman Palestin also distributed medical assistance to

warning and medical victims at the Orthopedic Office, Shifaa Hospital, and Al Wafa Al Ridwan and bought an ambulance. Malay campaign 2015, Aman Palestine has launched a cash waqf project of RM 50 and RM 100, if donors donate this amount, the donor will receive a waqf certificate. In the month of Ramadan 2015, Aman Palestine initiated two projects:

- i. Ramadhan with Aman Palestine. The presence of Palestinian imams in Malaysian mosques, the first charitable iftar, breaking the fast with Aman Palestine, and the first qiyamulail.
- ii. Ramadan with Palestine. Donors can contribute to the Palestinian people in the month of Ramadan through activities such as morning prayers at al-Aqsa, iftar, and Amirah prayers at al-Aqsa mosque as well as financial donations to Palestinian families.

After discussing the Aman Palestine projects above, the Reviewer believes that Aman Palestine has strategic initiatives in planning various types of projects. The long-term project is also an achievement for Makita to have a system of stability for the life of the Palestinian people forever (Aman, 2021).

Activities

Aman Palestine has various activities carried out at the central and national levels. However, the reviewers nekho raw activities for Safe Palestine with a focus on 2013 as healthy as 2015. On 1 March 2013 the Palestinian issue forum has been closed; 'Tribute to Palestine' was organized by the Putrajaya Carnival Organization and Safe Palestine in conjunction with Putrajaya. The forum presented Mahathir Mohammad who represented the Perdana Global Security Foundation and Zainur Rashid Zainuddin who represented the Aman Palestine negotiator. The Young Icon Night Program was the presenter on the forum "Palestine Bleeding in Our Manela" at the National University of Malaysia (UKM) Bangi on 21 March 2013 with three-panel experts: Mohd Azrin Samsudin (Safe Palestine), Salima Habibi (Ambassador of Safe Palestine) and Norazmi (Aqsa Sharif). The "Palestinian Night We Are With You" program was held on March 28, 2013, at Universiti Sains Islam Malaysia (USIM). The program's main slot is security parkantiya with Farah Adeeba who is the ambassador of Aman Palestine. Among the dance activities in the program are poetry presentations, sales, awards, lectures, multimedia workshops, and presentations of a collection of nasyid from One-Soulz. In 2013, Aman Palestine sent five expert doctors to perform operations in Gaza at the Gaza Medicine Mission (Agrawal, Testi, Bodaghi, et al., 2021).

Aman Palestin also opens sales and exhibitions in public programs organized by external parties. For example, on 12 April 2014 in conjunction with the "Book and ICT Party", Aman Palestine was at the PKNS Shah Alam Complex, and on 20 April 2014 at the Bangi Gateway Complex, Bandar Baru Bangi in the Bangi Islamic Festival. For the reviewers, opening a sales and exhibition booth like this is a good initiative because through it you can market compatibility to the common people with the provision of treatises and sikbaran by representatives of sales booths on the Palestinian issue. Among other programs, Safe Palestine is the "Seminar on Understanding Palestinian Issues" which was held on June 1, 2014, in Bandar Baru Bangi. This forum is friendly to know about food related to Palestinian issues with special interests, namely Hamad Abo Dabes (Chairman of the Arab Palestinians in the Negev), Samara Abd El Hakim (Director of the Palestinian Sharia Court), Freag (Naib President of the Islamic Movement in Palestine) and Rayan Kamel (Director of the Mahkama Palestinian Sharia) Palestinian Islamiyah) (Agrawal, Testi, Mahajan, et al., 2021).

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On September 21, 2014, a seminar "News from Gaza" was held at the Aman Palestine office, Shah Alam. The seminar was hosted by Omar Seyam (Chief Executive Officer of Safe Palestine in Palestine) and Hamza Deirawi (Palestinian Media Coordinator). In conjunction with the construction and rehabilitation of Gaza organized by the Sultan Salahuddin Abdul Aziz Shah Cultural and Arts Center, Universiti Putra Malaysia (UPM) in cooperation with Aman Palestine has organized a "One Million Voices Charity Night". This program was held on 3 October 2014 at UPM which also visited Mahathir Mohamad. Other examples of activities carried out by Aman Palestine are a series of excursions to Australia which was launched in May 2015 to share information among Malaysian students in Australia. Siri Jelajah was accompanied by Awang Sufian (Chief Executive Officer of Aman Palestine Malaysia), Muhammad Nazriq (Chairman of Safe Palestine Australia), and Heliza Helmi (Activist/Celebrity) and the areas that have been explored are Sydney, Brisbane, Hobart, Melbourne, and Adelaide. In addition, Aman Palestine has become the leader of the Palestinian imams to lead the Tarawikh prayers throughout the country in Malaysia in 2015. This program is an activity of Aman Palestine prisoners who have been doing it since 2012. On May 30, 2015, Busking4Palestine has been together with the Group Munada located at Morib Beach, Selangor. The purpose of this busking was held to collect skin for the Palestinian people. An example of Aman Palestine's active activities is that Hashimah Salleh (Salestin Safe Steering Committee Expert) was invited to the Tabayyun Program along with a chat session with Wan Kamaruddin from Astro Oasis on October 21, 2015. The interview was with a neighbor of Kepatan Terki in Palestine (F et al., 2018).

Aman Palestine also has various programs run by the central, state, and regional governments. The programs that are being carried out are not limited to Malaysia, but Safe Palestine has spread its wings by blocking activities outside the country in the generalization of the Palestinian issue to all stakeholders. However, the reviewers took part in the activities of Safe Palestine. Most of them focused more on those who believed in Islam only. If you want to attract the attention of many parties, Aman Palestine will be able to expand its activities (Aman, 2020).

Achievement

Among the utahita who are involved in Aman Palestine is Hashimah Salleh who is an expert on the Aman Palestine Steering Committee and has been remembered as a figure of Maal Hijrah in the state of Selangor. He was awarded because of his active involvement in Palestinian issues and frequent humanitarian missions to Gaza, Lebanon, and Palestinian refugee camps. In 2013, Abdullah Zaik (Executive Trustee of Safe Palestine) has already remembered Sultan Mizan Zainal Abidin who is the Sultan of Terengganu. The dedication was based on his dalaliya which he learned a lot together with the movement of Safe Palestine. Apart from that, this award also supports Abdullah Zaik's development in works that can make Malaysia proud, such as all humanitarian missions to Palestine, and Palestinian refugee camps in Lebanon and Syria (Strohm, 2019).

Apart from that, the achievement of Aman Palestine can be felt not only from celebrations or other organizational institutions but also from the media that have recognized Aman Palestine as an organization that is active in humanitarian issues. The proof is when the media has given good recommendations to Aman Palestine such as TV3 and TV Al-Hijrah. For example, a series of 13 slot documentaries under "Mentari Palestine" broadcast the Al-

Hijrah crew's television entry into Gaza and the al-Aqsa mosque in collaboration with Aman Palestine to provide a clear picture of what is happening in Gaza to the Malaysian public (Silver, 2021).

Challenges in Struggle

Aman Palestine takes the same big aim if Aman Palestine as an agency, not a small kingdom is bound by a Zionist mission to serve as a humanitarian aid mission to Palestine. This matter is not only a one-way defense for Aman Palestine but also for other NGOs, which are quite different, whether they are from Malaysia or foreign countries. Aman Palestine admits that it is rather difficult to operate in the capacity of an NGO that wants to assist countries that do not support Israel. Things that hinder Safe Palestine are how to get into Gaza. According to him, many NGOs who like to strengthen humanitarian missions to Gaza are protected from the obstacles of Israeli exenteration. This challenge can be seen if the Gaza gate is opened through the Egyptian highway towards Israel. Belayu stated that Israel had also made an entry into international waters such as the incident on the Mavi Marmara ship, even though it managed to enter international waters, it was still detained and attacked by Israeli soldiers (Minardi & Hasanah, 2019).

The world is forced to deal with the politics played by Israel when dealing with a conspiracy that threatens Israel. But what is a nakara when apaila matatu comes from the United States, the United Nations, and the great powers? Even though the Malaysian people are facing economic problems and the Malaysian people are suffering, they still don't know what they Malaysian people are doing. that with the expanse of wealth, the property will be enriched again and the result is that the generosity of the Malaysian people is still not through Aman Palestine. However, many Malaysians see what is happening in Palestine based on the issues currently affecting the Palestinian people at certain times. The Malaysian people will be aware and willing to donate if they put Israel over Gaza. For example, in July 2014, a large number of Malaysians were contiguous, so the dispute was not traded (Shawahna et al., 2017).

However, if there is no Israeli attack on Gaza, then the situation will be as usual. But until now, Israel has messed up the construction of the al-Aqsa mosque and this has become the biggest issue because the al-Aqsa mosque itself is Palestinian. Unfortunately, this tyranny was unable to raise the awareness of the Malaysian people about Israel's tyranny. This is because the reviewer thinks that the people of Malaysia understand more about Israel's tyranny when it strikes against Palestine even though no war of tyranny is not heard through the media, such as the siege of the al-Aqsa mosque, Israel's general turmoil against the Palestinian people and partitions requiring the principle of not keeping order from the people of Malaysia, while the Palestinian people are still struggling and still asking for financial assistance from outside parties (Kitamura et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The unheard-of suffering of the Palestinian people under the conquest and tyranny of the Zionists has succeeded in attracting the catamaran of the world community to participate in solidarity in achieving the mandate's superior rights as a single state without ownership. If you pay close attention, the issue of Palestine is not just a regional name among Muslims in

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Indonesia and Malaysia, it has also joined the Angara promotion of non-Islamic groups such as in the city of London, the United States, Germany, Français, and Japan. This civil wave community at the same time gives the opportunity to inter-ajang NGOs to channel their mutual assistance to humanity, whether through advocacy or operations. For Aman Palestine, the reviewer considers this NGO to be more operational and mobilize various forms of humanitarian assistance in Palestine in an emergency and for a long time to ensure the survival of the people of Sana can continue even if there is a shortage. service. Projects such as fostered are also seen as not only giving assistance to them but also asking them to generate their data without waiting for outside help. The implementation project is also not only focused on the Gaza area but is also being carried out in other areas such as Khan Younis, Jabalia, Bani Suhaila, and Al Shouka.

The work done by Aman Palestine deserves a thumbs up because many international NGOs are more focused on projects in Gaza than in other areas, while that area is also affected by the Israeli occupation. The activities carried out in Malaysia to reach and spread awareness about the issue of Palestine to the people here have given many positive feedbacks for Aman Palestine and continue to work to help the Palestinian people. Even though there is a ban on activists, especially when facing the threat of Zionism in Gaza, they do not allow Aman Palestine to continue carrying out human rights activities. On the other hand, various achievements have been achieved by some members of Safe Palestine as a sign that this culture of the organization is driving the organization in a better direction.

However, after examining in depth the form of the Safe Palestine project that is being carried out in Palestine, it can be seen that the implementation of this project is being carried out among the Palestinian community who are Muslim, and many people are Christians in Palestine. Just like the activities carried out in Malaysia, most of them are religious. Consciousness among Muslims is only non-Muslims like in China and India. The reviewer wants to point here and there that the Palestinian humanization issue is not a religious issue but a universal humanization issue because in that land there are also people who are not Muslims. Thus, the Reviewer suggested that Malaysian Humanitarian NGOs that carry the issue of Palestine, especially organizations managed by those who are Muslim, need to be open in their struggle so that this coalition can have an impact on Israel to get out of Palestinian land.

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